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08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
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08.00.11 Marketing
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SPECIFIC FEATURES OF MIGRATION FROM UZBEKISTAN AND PROSPECTS FOR ORGANIZATIONAL IMPROVEMENT

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Abstract: This article examines the demographic and socio-economic challenges driving migration flows from Uzbekistan. Key factors include high fertility rates, a significant share of unemployed labor force, underdeveloped rural infrastructure, and comparatively low regional wages. The study emphasizes how these structural issues contribute to both internal and external migration dynamics. In conclusion, the article outlines policy recommendations aimed at enhancing the regulation of labor mobility and ensuring the safety and protection of migrant workers.

Key words: Labor migration, demographic imbalances, labor supply, infrastructure, demographic potential, remittances, wages.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistondan migratsiya oqimlarini yuzaga keltiruvchi demografik va ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy muammolar tahlil qilinadi. Asosiy omillar sifatida yuqori tug'ilish ko'rsatkichi, ishsiz mehnat resurslari ulushining kattaligi, qishloq infratuzilmasining rivojlanmaganligi va mintaqaviy ish haqlarining pastligi ko'rsatib o'tiladi. Tadqiqotda ushbu tarkibiy muammolar ichki va tashqi migratsiya jarayonlariga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishi yoritilgan. Yakunda esa mehnat migratsiyasini tartibga solishni takomillashtirish hamda mehnat muhojirlarining xavfsizligi va huquqlarini ta'minlash bo'yicha tavsiyalar ilgari surilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Mehnat migratsiyasi, demografik nomutanosibliklar, mehnat taklifi, infratuzilma, demografik salohiyat, pul o'tkazmalari, ish haqi.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются демографические и социально-экономические вызовы, определяющие миграционные потоки из Узбекистана. К ключевым факторам относятся высокий уровень рождаемости, значительная доля безработной рабочей силы, недостаточно развитая сельская инфраструктура и относительно низкий уровень региональной заработной платы. В исследовании подчеркивается, как эти структурные проблемы влияют на внутреннюю и внешнюю миграцию. В заключение приведены рекомендации по совершенствованию регулирования трудовой мобильности и обеспечению безопасности и защиты трудовых мигрантов.

Ключевые слова: Трудовая миграция, демографические дисбалансы, предложение рабочей силы, инфраструктура, демографический потенциал, денежные переводы, заработная плата.

INTRODUCTION

The role of migration in the economic development of participating countries has significantly increased in recent decades. Moreover, the twenty-first century is becoming the "century of global migration." [1]

Economic factors, such as the availability of jobs with higher wages and the lack of opportunities for self-realization in the domestic labor market, influence the decision to migrate. Social factors also play a considerable role, particularly the opportunity to obtain a prestigious education abroad as a springboard for further career development either in the host country or upon return to the country of origin, supported by improved foreign language proficiency.

In the era of globalization, the formation of migration flows has also been shaped by the information factor (the rapid development of the Internet) and the affordability of air travel.

Demographic imbalances that have emerged over recent decades also exert a strong impact on migration processes. Specifically, population growth in developing countries and its decline in developed states have become key drivers. According to forecasts, by 2050, more than 86% of the world’s population will live in developing countries. In the poorest of these countries, the population may double over the next 20 years due to high fertility rates.

Population decline in developed countries is largely driven by falling fertility rates, which are associated with changing attitudes toward childbearing, the declining value of children, and the greater involvement of women in social and economic life. As a result, most economically advanced countries, facing a demographic crisis, have adopted policies aimed at stimulating fertility and encouraging migration to offset labor shortages.

Uzbekistan is among the countries with high fertility rates. According to the Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the country leads the CIS in fertility. In 2024, the fertility rate was 24.9 births per 1,000 population, followed by Kazakhstan (23.5), Kyrgyzstan (22.4), Armenia (12.4), Azerbaijan (11.2), Moldova (11.2), and Russia (9.6) [2].

This situation exacerbates the problem of employment. Currently, more than 600,000 young people enter Uzbekistan’s labor market each year, and by 2030, this number is expected to reach 1 million. At the same time, according to the Ministry of Labor of Uzbekistan, as of July 1, 2024, the country had 876,000 unemployed persons, representing 5.8% of the economically active population [2].

Furthermore, half of Uzbekistan’s population lives in rural areas, where agriculture remains the primary source of income, though labor demand is limited. Socioeconomic disparities in these regions have also revealed pressing infrastructural problems, such as access to gas, electricity, heating, and potable water, as well as overall water scarcity for irrigating household plots intended for growing fruits, vegetables, and traditional crafts that constitute vital sources of livelihood in rural areas.

As a result, in search of better living conditions, a significant share of the working-age rural population migrates to Tashkent, contributing to an increase in internal migration. World Bank experts confirm this trend, noting that migration is more widespread among lower-income groups and rural households.

Properly regulated migration can generate positive effects for host countries – by alleviating labor shortages, stimulating economic growth, improving the demographic balance, and enriching social and cultural life – as well as for sending countries, by boosting remittance flows that enhance domestic consumption and demand. Conversely, unregulated migration can stimulate the growth of the shadow economy, increase crime rates, depress local wages, and exacerbate interethnic and interreligious tensions [1].

Thus, under current conditions, the world faces the urgent need to develop a fundamentally new approach to migration governance at the global level. This study will be devoted to addressing this challenge.

This article, to a certain extent, serves to fulfill the objectives provided for in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-158 dated September 11, 2023 “On the Strategy “Uzbekistan – 2030” [3], No. UP-162 dated October 17, 2024 “On priority measures to reform the migration management system” [4], in the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 252 dated April 22, 2025 “On measures to further improve the system of organized employment of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan abroad” [5], the Order of the Minister of Employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 10, 2018 “On approval of the regulation on the procedure for voluntary registration of citizens traveling abroad to carry out labor activities, as well as carrying out labor activities abroad under private labor contracts” [6] and other regulatory and legal documents in this area.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The growing challenges of migration have been addressed in the works of numerous scholars. Of particular note are the studies of Ryazantsev S. and Bozhenko V.[1], who analyzed socio-demographic groups of the population that had previously shown low mobility, as well as alarming phenomena such as the exploitation of migration flows by transnational criminal networks, resulting in migrants becoming victims of organized crime.

Grozin A. [2] raises concerns by highlighting both economic and demographic imbalances—using the example of Uzbekistan’s regions – as one of the key drivers of internal migration within the country.

Of particular interest are the studies conducted by experts of the “Development Strategy” Center, Zh. Sharipov and R. Nuriddinov [7] propose mechanisms for ensuring orderly and safe labor migration.

From a broader European perspective, Christos Bagavos [8] offers methodological and empirical insights into the role of migration in shaping the European labor market. His analysis shows that between 2006 and 2018, growth in European labor force participation was predominantly driven by foreign-born individuals, underscoring the structural significance of migration for sustaining labor markets against demographic pressures.

Additionally, Giovanni Peri [9], an Italian-American economist, explores labor market dynamics in Western Europe. His work indicates that while immigration may adversely affect employment among existing immigrants,

its overall impact on native workers is minimal. Moreover, he finds that immigration encourages native workers to transition into more complex occupations, increasing their wages – demonstrating that immigrants can indirectly contribute to native labor upgrading

Despite the diversity of existing research on the challenges posed by labor migration, in the current socio-economic context of Uzbekistan – characterized by rapid population growth rooted in historically established reproductive patterns and the structural composition of the population – the insufficiently effective utilization of demographic potential has become evident. This lacuna necessitates further scholarly investigation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In conducting this study, a combination of qualitative and analytical methods was employed. The methods of observation and comparison were used to examine the dynamics of migration flows and to identify similarities and differences in the socio-economic conditions influencing them. In addition, the methods of analysis and synthesis were applied to systematize theoretical concepts and empirical findings related to labor migration.

Furthermore, the study makes use of the statistical method, which enabled the processing and interpretation of demographic and labor market data obtained from national and international sources. The comparative-historical method was also applied to trace the evolution of migration trends in Uzbekistan within the broader context of global migration processes.

The theoretical significance of the research lies in substantiating the necessity of conducting targeted marketing studies to identify in-demand professions abroad and the corresponding expected wages, as well as in emphasizing the importance of strengthening the role of regional administrations (khokimiyats) in the effective organization of labor migration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As of January 2024, the total number of labor migrants from Uzbekistan was estimated at 2 million people. Among them, 1,452,300 were men (72.4%) and 547,700 were women (27.6%).

The Russian Federation remains the primary destination, accounting for 60% of all Uzbek migrants, or approximately 1.2 million individuals. The distribution of other destinations is as follows (see Table 1): Kazakhstan – 191.8 thousand people (10%), Turkey – 113.8 thousand people (6%), the Republic of Korea – 68.1 thousand people (3%), and other countries – 424.4 thousand people (21%) [7].

It is most likely that Russia and Kazakhstan are chosen as destinations primarily for geographical reasons and linguistic accessibility, despite the somewhat altered status of the Russian language compared to the Soviet period. At present, a portion of Uzbekistan’s population speaks Russian at a basic, everyday level, which is generally characterized by a limited vocabulary and frequent errors in pronunciation and grammar [10].

Table 1. Migration from Uzbekistan: number and share of migrants as of January 1, 2024 (in millions and %)

Total, in million people	Russia	in %	Kazakhstan	in %	Turkey	in %	South Korea	in %	Other countries	in %
2,0	1,2	60,0	0,19	10,0	0,12	6	0,07	3,0	0,42	21

As of 2025, estimates of the Russian-speaking population in Uzbekistan vary considerably: according to different sources, between 18.5% and 70% of the population is reported to possess Russian language skills. These significant discrepancies arise from differences in measurement criteria – some studies take into account only active use of the language, while others also include passive competence (the ability to understand speech and texts without regular verbal interaction).

By contrast, linguistic similarity (as Turkish and Uzbek both belong to the Turkic language family and share common grammatical, phonetic, and lexical features), religious affiliation, and visa-free entry encourage 6% of Uzbek citizens to migrate to Turkey in search of better employment opportunities.

In addition, the introduction of simplified procedures for obtaining work visas in the Republic of Korea – through direct applications to city administrations—has influenced migration choices. Citizens who complete three-month professional training courses combined with instruction in the Korean language are now able to obtain work visas and secure employment in Korea. This policy has encouraged Uzbek migrants to view Korea as a viable destination for labor migration. While their share remains relatively small (3% of the total number of external migrants), Korea consistently ranks fourth in popularity among preferred host countries.

Table 2. Distribution of labor migrants from Uzbekistan by sector of employment abroad (as of January 1, 2024, %) [7]

Construction	52,7
Industry	12,8
Services	9,7
Catering	6,9
Trade	6,7
Transport	4,3
Agriculture	4,1
Other industries	2,8
Total	100,0

Abroad, Uzbek labor migrants most frequently apply their skills in the construction of buildings, roads, bridges, and other infrastructure projects; in manufacturing industries; and in the service sector, including cleaning, food preparation, childcare, and eldercare. They are also engaged in public catering as general workers, cooks, waiters, bartenders in cafes and restaurants, and couriers for food delivery services. In the trade sector, migrants often work in markets and retail outlets, while in transport, they are employed as drivers and loaders. In agriculture, they contribute to crop harvesting, livestock care, and other branches of the rural economy.

The sectoral and geographical distribution of Uzbek labor migrants reflects both domestic labor oversupply in low- and medium-skilled occupations and international demand for affordable labor in construction, manufacturing, agriculture, and services. Russia and Kazakhstan remain the leading destinations, primarily due to geographical proximity, cultural familiarity, and linguistic accessibility. Although the status of the Russian language has changed since the Soviet era, its residual role continues to shape migration choices: a considerable portion of Uzbekistan’s population retains at least a basic knowledge of Russian, albeit often limited in vocabulary and marked by pronunciation or grammatical errors. Current estimates of the Russian-speaking population vary widely – from 18.5% to 70%, depending on whether studies consider only active language use or also include passive competence.

By contrast, Turkey attracts about 6% of Uzbek migrants, supported by linguistic similarity between Turkish and Uzbek (both belonging to the Turkic language family), shared religious affiliation, and the advantage of visa-free entry. The Republic of Korea, though accounting for only 3% of Uzbek labor migrants, has emerged as a notable destination thanks to simplified visa procedures, short-term professional and language training programs, and structured recruitment channels.

Sectorally, Uzbek migrants abroad are concentrated in construction (buildings, roads, bridges, and infrastructure), manufacturing, agriculture, and a wide range of service industries. In catering and retail, they work as cooks, waiters, bartenders, and couriers, while in transport, they serve as drivers and loaders. In agriculture, they contribute to crop harvesting, livestock management, and related activities. This occupational concentration highlights both the limited absorption capacity of Uzbekistan’s domestic labor market and the continuing demand abroad for flexible, relatively low-cost migrant labor.

Remittances from abroad sent by labor migrants not only provide essential financial support to large families, helping them to stay afloat, but also stimulate domestic demand and consumption while contributing to the stability of the national currency [11]. Thus, remittances from so-called “gastarbeiters” play a crucial role in Uzbekistan’s economy.

According to the results of 2024, the total volume of remittances to Uzbekistan increased by almost 30%, reaching 14.8 billion USD. Transfers from Russia grew by 29%, despite the number of Uzbek migrants in this country decreasing by 1.7 times due to the ongoing special military operation. At the same time, remittances from the United States rose by 35%, from the United Kingdom by 1.8 times, and from South Korea by 1.6 times [12].

The Central Bank associates the upward trend in remittances with the strengthening of partner countries’ currencies and the redirection of migration flows towards higher-income destinations. In the first quarter of the current year alone, Uzbekistan received 3.3 billion USD, which is 32% more than in the same period of the previous year. For the period 2025–2027, remittances are forecast to grow annually by 10–15% “within the framework of a fundamental trend,” potentially reaching 20 billion USD [13].

Figure 1. Forecast of Remittance Inflows to Uzbekistan (2025–2027, in USD billions)

Thus, given the current socio-economic situation in the country and the importance of youth employment, the geography of migration is expanding. "In 2025 alone, it is planned to facilitate the employment of more than 200,000 citizens in 21 economically developed countries, including Germany, the United Kingdom, Japan, the Republic of Korea, Israel, Canada, Poland, Turkey, Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, and others," stated the head of government [14].

The Government of Uzbekistan is pursuing diversification of labor migration markets in order to expand the list of destination countries and reduce dependence on one or several main directions. In the coming years, this work will continue through the creation of conditions for citizens wishing to work abroad, including training in professional skills and foreign languages, as emphasized by the Prime Minister.

In addition, new measures are being introduced to support and prepare labor migrants. For instance, to further strengthen cooperation between St. Petersburg and the Samarkand region, an agreement was reached to secure the social and medical rights of Uzbek citizens and to ensure safe and orderly migration [15].

Alongside measures aimed at supporting migrants abroad, important trends have also emerged regarding the return of labor migrants to Uzbekistan. Recently, the government invited citizens, including those working abroad, to participate in the construction of New Tashkent. Recruitment was carried out across 38 construction-related professions, including bricklayers, plumbers, and electricians, with reported wages ranging from 8 to 15 million soums [16].

In October 2024, during a visit to the Tashkent region, the President expressed his view on the employment of Uzbek citizens abroad: "If they earn 1,500–2,000 dollars, that is excellent, and we will support them. If they earn less than this amount, it is better to create conditions for them here" [17].

Overall, the government's dual strategy – on the one hand, diversifying external labor markets, and on the other, encouraging the return of qualified workers – may serve as a stabilizing factor for Uzbekistan's labor market. Diversification reduces vulnerability to external shocks and geopolitical risks, while reintegration of returning migrants helps to mitigate domestic unemployment and transfer valuable skills acquired abroad into the national economy. In the long run, this approach could contribute not only to economic sustainability but also to the balanced development of human capital in Uzbekistan.

CONCLUSION

Labor migration remains one of the key socio-economic processes in Uzbekistan, directly influencing household welfare, labor market dynamics, and national economic stability. While remittances significantly contribute to poverty reduction and domestic consumption, challenges related to migrants' legal literacy, professional mismatch, and weak institutional support persist. The following policy recommendations are proposed to ensure safe, orderly, and beneficial migration processes. They are structured around key problems, objectives, and policy instruments, aligning state priorities with international best practices.

Table 3. Policy recommendations for ensuring safe, orderly, and beneficial labor migration

Problem	Goal	Policy Instrument
Low legal awareness of labor migrants	Enhance legal literacy and protection of labor rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mandatory pre-departure training on host-country labor legislation • Online legal education platforms • Joint programs of the Ministry of Justice and the Ministry of Employment
Skills mismatch with foreign labor market demand	Align migrants' qualifications with international labor market needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Labor market research on in-demand professions abroad • Development of targeted vocational and language training • Coordination between the Ministry of Higher Education and international partners
Insufficient monitoring of migrants' working conditions abroad	Strengthen supervision and institutional responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Performance indicators for regional authorities (hokimiyats) • Unified digital database of migrants • Enhanced role of diplomatic missions in monitoring
Limited access to counseling and support services	Improve social protection of migrants and their families	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of info-consultation centers in Uzbekistan and host countries • 24/7 hotlines and online advisory platforms • Engagement of NGOs and diaspora communities
Lack of bilateral agreements on migrant protection	Expand international cooperation and legal guarantees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New bilateral agreements on social and medical security • Strengthened negotiations with the EU, South Korea, Japan, Gulf states • Active involvement of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and the Ministry of Employment
Challenges in the reintegration of returning migrants	Facilitate the reintegration and economic utilization of migrants' potential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preferential loans for entrepreneurship • Requalification and start-up support programs • Employment opportunities in national projects (e.g., "New Tashkent" construction initiative)

Implementation of these policy recommendations will contribute to the development of a safer, more transparent, and economically efficient migration system in Uzbekistan. Strengthened legal literacy, diversified migration destinations, and improved reintegration programs are expected to reduce risks of labor exploitation, enhance the stability of remittance inflows, and maximize the socio-economic benefits of migration for both migrants and the national economy.

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